

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF IDIOMATIC EXPRESSIONS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This article has a main purpose to explore the role of idiomatic expressions and their underlying nature in English language and analyzes alternatives of expressions in other foreign languages.

Key words: Idiomatic expressions, figurative language, linguistic phenomena, English language, categorization, lingua franca

INTRODUCTION

Idiom is considered as a linguistic phenomenon, denoting the group of words with a figurative, non-literal meaning which cannot be apprehended by looking at its individual words. Throughout the history of linguistics, a plethora of linguists have bestowed diverse interpretations of idioms. According to Gajda (1993.p5), "Idioms are a complicated expressions, in which the gist is inseparably associated with some of metaphorical meaning. Also Dastjerdi and Alipour (2010), in delineating the role and importance of idioms, indicated that non-native students could seem aberrant if they have not got sufficient knowledge in using idiomatic language. While exploring the essence of idioms this thought comes to our mind: why do we need idioms in English and are they crucial in accelerating the process of learning written and spoken English? According to statistics, there are more than 25,000 idioms in English language. So what are some examples of idioms that many native speakers use in their colloquial language and that multitude English language learners try to learn? Some alternative variants comprise:

- 1.To wine and dine-to take someone out for an evening or an expensive meal
- 2.To wrap up -to finish
- 3.Dragon lady-a nasty woman who misuses her power
4. On a shoestring- on a very low budget
- 5.Nuts and bolts -details; basic components of something
- 6.To rant and rave- to talk loudly, often in anger
- 7.Fair and square -honestly
- 8.Big shot-a powerful or important person
- 9.Like pulling teeth- very complicated
- 10.To pitch in-to help

In fact, idioms are linguistic phenomena that mean more than a shorter way of saying the same thing. It is undoubtedly true that idiomatic expressions are considered as a tool that proliferates the expressiveness of the diversity of the utterance. This figurative language is such a wonderful tool that we can use them to express negative thoughts in a humorous way. For instance, rather than writing about a character who is a stupid or silly and not able to normally, it is preferable to say “daft as a brush” or “to have nothing between one’s ears”. These idioms seem to be softer and less affronting. With the help of these, you can also imagine the occurrences and may feel yourself in that condition: “The victor of this world championship feel like she is walking on air”. In this sentence the idiom “walking on air” means “happy”. The most renowned litterateurs in literature used expressions to append sarcasm to their writing. A significant number of idioms is acknowledged in the lines of popular artistic works. There are several examples of this:

1. “The world is my oyster”- this idiom was first mentioned in the work “The Merry Wives of Windsor”. In today’s lexicon, this phrase denotes that you can do anything that you want to.

2. “There is method in my madness” – there is a line in the play “Hamlet” that uses this phrase. Currently, this idiom means that “there is some kind of reason behind someone’s mysterious character.

3. But natheless, betwixt earnest and game,
He at the last appointed him on one,
And let all others from his hearte gon,
And chose her of his own authority;
For love is blind all day and may not see

(Canterbury Tales by Geoffrey Chaucer)

In this frame narrative, Chaucer uses this figurative language “love is blind” to emphasize that the love-struck man does not see the demerits of his beloved.

Categorization of English idioms

Idioms, which are part of phraseology in the linguistics, are divided into 4 types: pure idioms, binomial idioms, partial idioms and prepositional idioms. This article provides an elucidation and samples of each type of idiom and how they can be differentiated from each other.

1. Pure idioms are expressions whose original meaning has been lost or forgotten and thus, it is not feasible to analyze these expressions logically. Examples of pure idioms. There are several examples in this category: Break a

leg (Good luck!), once in a blue moon (seldom), three sheets to the wind (tipsy or inebriate).

2. Binomial idioms often comprises two words which are interconnected with the help of conjunctions (“and”, “or”). In this type of idioms, the word order is stable. Examples: chalk and cheese (used in delineating two things which are disparate), wine and dine (eat and drink well), there and then (occurs instantly), in dribs and drabs (in small quantities), laughter and tears (blessedness and affliction).

3. Partial idioms have two parts: a literal part and a non-literal part. Example: “When in Rome, do as the Romans do” means that when you are in other place, you should adopt their customs and traditions as your own.

4. Prepositional idioms embraces prepositions with certain nouns, phrases and verbs in order to create this figurative language. Prepositional idioms are abundant in English language: out of harm’s away (secure), out of work (jobless), by all means (explicitly, certainly), from time to time (sometimes, now and then).

The current paper scrutinizes deeply some idiomatic expressions in English and their French, German, Uzbek equivalents. The purpose is to scientifically and theoretically confirm that these idioms exist not only in one language, but also in other languages with an in-depth approach.

English idioms with Uzbek equivalent

English idioms	Uzbek equivalent	Meaning
Rain cats and dogs	Chelaklab yomg’ir yog’moq	To rain very heavily
A piece of cake	Xamirdan qil sug’urgandek	Something that is very easy to accomplish
To be over the moon	Og’zi qulog’ida	Very happy
To kill two birds with one stone	Bir o’q bilan ikki quyinni o’ldirmoq	To attain two things with the one action
To lose one’s temper	Tepa sochi tikka bo’lmoq	To become very angry
When pigs fly	Tuyaning dumi yerga tekkanda	Something that will never occur

English idioms with French equivalent

English idioms	French equivalent	Meaning
To cost an arm and a leg	Ça coûte un bras	Very expensive

To feel blue	Avoir le cafard	To feel sad
A bird in the hand is worth two in the bush	Un chien vivant vaut mieux qu'un lion mort	It is better to have a small secured advantage than the possibility of a bigger one
Every cloud has a silver lining	À quelque -chose malheur est bon Après la pluie le beau temps	A negative incident could have a positive aspect to it

In our globalized world, English language has been evolving significantly around the globe and unquestionably been reckoned as lingua franca of the world. It has been effectuated completely due to its uniqueness. English is a kind of lingua, which is affluent in idioms. Idioms and slang offer us an insight into language that goes beyond basic communication: they combine culture and history and create words that often work as a type of code or understanding for those that exist within a certain community. Idioms may be utilized in both verbal and written communication. Comprehending distinctive lingo's idioms is consequential because they demand a broader familiarity of the language to perceive what someone signifies when we use them in discourse. Idioms are absolutely beneficial since they give individuals a new, efficacious and creative way to express themselves. In this position, one thing should be mentioned that idioms can also be utterly humorous to user, which enables us to express ourselves in a more genuine way, embracing a sense of humour and showing off our personality. Idioms can help ameliorate our conversational skills because it demonstrates native speakers that you realize the cultural meaning and context behind the idiom you are using. In fact, this figurative language helps to showcase the English proficiency with the native peers. This make the discourse more hilarious and less monotonous.

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